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Quality assurance at Faculty level: finding the balance between HEI-accreditation and transnational programme-accreditation

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INTRODUCTION

The Faculty of Engineering Science at XXX has a longstanding tradition in engineering education. A wide variety of different engineering programmes are offered both at the Bachelor's level (2), at the Master's level (23) and at the Advanced Master's level (6). Over 3,000 students are trained in line with an academic tradition in which education is strongly based on research. The quality of the education is a top priority of the Faculty.

The Faculty strongly wishes to aim for quality assurance at an international level through a transnational accreditation by an international agency. However, because the Faculty is embedded in a major university, which houses about 60 000 students across 16 faculties, the requirements of the national institutional review of XXX (HEI-level) also have to be met.

The Faculty developed a quality assurance system where the standards of transnational accreditation as well as the national Higher Education Institutional review were fulfilled. Several challenges were encountered during this development: the 4-year cycle of the national HEI-accreditation had to be integrated in the six-year cycle of the transnational agency; the need for customized quality assurance of the different programmes of the faculty had to be

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acknowledged. Two main cornerstones for faculty quality assurance were defined: a strong involvement of all stakeholders and well-considered curriculum development.

This paper will describe the resulting quality assurance system, the instruments integrated and choices made.

1. HEI-ACCREDITATION VS TRANSNATIONAL PROGRAMME ACCREDITATION?

HEI-accreditation

In June 2015, the Flemish Parliament approved a revision to the system of quality assurance and accreditation in higher education, with an evolution towards full institutional accreditation in 2020 and a suspension of the previous programme accreditation system. The institutional review is a periodic assessment of the quality of the educational policy pursued by an institution. The Accreditation Organisation of the Netherlands and Flanders (NVAO) commissions an external panel to conduct the review.

As described in the Framework for Institutional reviews [1], this review enables the institution to demonstrate the vision from which it operates, the policy it pursues, the achievements resulting from that policy, the measures for improvement it has taken, and new policy it has developed. Each institution chooses a structure and quality culture that suits its vision. As a component of an organisational culture, the quality culture is focused on continuous quality improvement. It is reflected in an institution-wide quality assurance system and thus constitutes the foundation of the quality of an institution's educational policy as well as the actual education provided.

Also XXX installed its own institution-wide quality assurance system, called COBRA. COBRA stands for Cooperation, Reflection and Action, with attention for Checks and Balances. COBRA starts from having confidence in the discipline-specific quality culture of every education programme and faculty. The programme committee is the pivot in this continuous process of quality development. A quality culture such as COBRA attributes ownership to the programme's primary actors: students, teachers and staff. Systematically, these actors engage in an open dialogue with external stakeholders: alumni, professionals in the field and (inter)national experts in the discipline. COBRA engages in a substantive dialogue about education and the necessary preconditions to support good education, and this at three levels of the university: education programme, faculty and institution. Throughout three cycles, COBRA ensures preconditions are adjusted at the appropriate level and feedback is given to adjacent levels. Transparency and public availability of information about the quality of education are necessary conditions for a sound quality culture. Quality assurance reports are published on the public website 'quality report'. [2]

At the end of 2016, a review panel visited XXX. During a first site visit, they formed an image on the vision for education and the way in which XXX shapes its educational policy and quality assurance. During a second site visit, the review panel focused on how theory is put into practice. They visited faculties, spoke to teaching staff and students, and attended several Programme Committee meetings. KU Leuven received a favourable report.

Transnational programme-accreditation

As described by Remaud et al. in 2017 [3], already in 2010 Flemish universities acknowledged the opportunities and benefits of a transnational accreditation and sought contact with CTI. CTI or "Commission des titres d'ingénieur" (CTI) is a French accreditation organization and is

equally composed of representatives of employers and professional engineers and academia [4]. CTI is also a member of ENQA (European Network for Quality Assurance) and EQAR (European Quality Assurance Register). Furthermore CTI is authorised by ENAEE (European Network for Accreditation of the Engineering Education) to award the EUR-ACE label. Under the aegis of the Flemish Interuniversity Council (VLIR), CTI and the Flemish faculties set a procedure, based on an agreed Terms of Reference (TOR). As described above, even before the start of the visitation and accreditation procedure, a change occurred in the legal context. However, even though they were no longer legally required to, all Flemish engineering faculties decided to go on and to ask CTI to execute the visitation and accreditation of their programmes. SER's were finalized in December 2014, CTI visited the Faculty in February 2015. For the Faculty, this visitation process was a strong momentum. The preparation and the writing of the SER gave the Faculty and its programmes a good mirror.

1.1 Integration of both systems

In the aftermath of the first visitation and accreditation cycle and the simultaneous changes in legal context, the Faculty was forced to reflect on the Faculty quality assurance system as such. Should the Faculty limit its quality assurance system to the obligatory HEI-accreditation and its accompanying COBRA-system? Or is the transnational visitation and accreditation and –more specifically- the preparation process of the former, valuable and worthwhile enough so that both systems should be combined? And could these two systems be combined in an efficient way without creating excessive administrative workload?

Being part of XXX, a faculty needs to be in line with the institutional quality assurance system COBRA, implemented to develop a strong quality assurance culture university-wide and to meet the requirements of the institutional review system. As COBRA engages on a substantive dialogue on education at different levels, the vision and concerns of the faculty are also taken into account at all those levels.

The fact that the EUR-ACE label can be acquired through CTI is obviously a strong incentive for continuing with CTI. Nonetheless, the Faculty also acknowledges other aspects of added value resulting from the CTI-accreditation cycle. One main benefit of the whole process lies in the strong groundwork that was done, with a lot of attention for curriculum development. The process of CTI, including the table of contents of the SER, guided this reflection. The procedure involved all the Faculty staff for the self-assessment, resulting in an empowered quality assurance culture. Additionally, since this is an accreditation by engineers, receiving feedback by these international peers is believed to be very valuable, well-tailored and useful. So the Faculty decided to develop a quality assurance system where the standards of transnational accreditation as well as the national Higher Education Institutional review were fulfilled. The challenges that accompany this decision and the subsequent integration and implementation of both systems, will be discussed in the next paragraphs.

2. INTEGRATED FACULTY QUALITY ASSURANCE SYSTEM

The Faculty quality assurance system had to be designed in a way that prerequisites and standards of both review systems can be fulfilled in a meaningful, yet feasible way.

A first and rather practical challenge was the integration of the 4-year cycle of the national HEI-accreditation in the six-year cycle of the transnational agency. The different deadlines and deliverables had to be aligned. A second important challenge involved the sheer size of the Faculty and the significant differences in characteristics between the engineering

programmes. Workflow and exercises had to be developed in a way that they could be customized and adapted to each specific programme without creating massive workload for the Faculty staff. Therefore many already established actions and habits were revised, upgraded and structured in an integrated system. Finally it was the Faculty's explicit policy to make quality assurance more accessible to teaching staff and to all other stakeholders and to encourage them to participate in ongoing didactical debates. To realize the Faculty's vision on an integrated quality assurance system, quality assurance at the Faculty is embedded in the actions of the educational committees (ECs) and is based on two important pillars: large involvement of all the stakeholders on the one hand and well thought-out developments of the curriculum on the other.

2.1. Cornerstones

Achieving a strong involvement of all stakeholders

Over the last decade, HEI's are slowly moving from a collegial to corporatist mode, where the roles of various stakeholders are being fundamentally redefined [5]. In order to be successful when involving stakeholders in quality assurance, Assif and Raouf [6] remarked that because of the complex nature of the new customer-supplier relationship, HEIs need to include stakeholder perspectives when designing the programme instead of "making arrow attempts to identify and address customer requirements only". Therefore, as earlier described by Wyns et al. [7], it is strongly recommended to involve stakeholders at every level of the programmes' design and updates, rather than consulting them at the final stages of the quality assurance process. Both intense cooperation and keeping a careful eye on the HEI's own interests seems to be necessary.

In the preparation of a first visitation and accreditation cycle by CTI, the Faculty, stated that all quality measures need to be implemented systematically. Existing means of consulting stakeholders were inventoried and large differences between the Faculty's departments were noticed. Several scenarios were therefore devised, depending on protocols the departments already had in place, and supervised actions which were taken to improve stakeholder participation. At first, four main groups of important stakeholders were identified: students, teachers, representatives of industry and alumni. More recently, the Faculty also recognised the importance of involving different groups of employees such as teaching assistants, student counsellors, ombudspersons and administrative support staff as well.

Pursuing a well-considered curriculum development

Curriculum development forms a vital aspect of a quality assurance process, as it is important for each programme to be sharply profiled and to form a clear identity. It allows for overlap, to be spotted both in form and in content.

A systematic approach in developing, maintaining and defining all the programmes enables the entire Faculty to discuss and exchange experiences at the same level. This causes quality assurance to be more accessible to teachers, teaching assistants and other stakeholders. In this way participation in ongoing educational debates is encouraged. Additionally a systematic approach to profiling programmes, formulating programme outcomes, clarifying learning objectives and subsequently executing curriculum mappings, entails the involvement of as many teachers as possible, thus creating a common plane on programme profile and programme programme outcomes. [8] Also the sheer size of the engineering faculty and the different characteristics of the different programmes, made a thoroughly systematic approach to curriculum development necessary.

A systematic approach needs a flexible and transparent framework. Since the Faculty had a positive experience with the AQCA framework in the context of benchmarking, it was a logical next step to use this framework for curriculum development.

The ACQA framework distinguishes seven areas of competence that characterize an engineer. It was inspired by a competence-based approach and was developed specifically for technological programmes and is based on the Dublin descriptors². The use of this framework makes it feasible for all stakeholders to discuss programme outcomes, programmes and other educational matters in a recognisable and transparent way and using the same terminology. [9] Based on ACQA, a three-step approach to curriculum development was therefore designed:

1. Formulating programme outcomes
2. Performing a curriculum mapping and developing competence profiles
3. Composing or updating ECTS-course descriptions

This three-step approach serves several purposes and the implementation thereof will be discussed further in this paper.

2.2. Implementation and instruments

At the Faculty, quality assurance is embedded in so called 'Educational Committees' (ECs): each EC is responsible for the coordination of one (cluster of) programme(s) and typically meets four to six times a year. Besides the organization, development and implementation of a coherent curriculum, the key mission of an EC is the quality assurance of its programme(s). All ECs are chaired by a programme director, and all programme directors take part in the Faculty Educational Committee (FEC), which is chaired by the vice-dean of Education. At Faculty level, the FEC is responsible for quality assurance and all associated actions, and can therefore be considered as an important part of the Faculty management. To facilitate and support the FEC and EC working of the Faculty, a team of staff members and project assistants specialized in educational issues, is employed. This team is called the Faculty Educational Development Unit (FEDU).

As discussed earlier, the substantive dialogue on the quality of education and the programmes is a basic requirement for creating a culture of quality. That is why the Faculty and its programmes commits itself to engage in conversation with all stakeholders involved at regular intervals (*involvement of all stakeholders*).

- Students are involved every two years through student conversations. During these conversations, students independently engage in conversation about the strengths and points of improvement of their programme. The student union is in charge of the organization of the conversations and is supported in this task by the FEDU. The results and information gained from the conversations are supplemented with the results from two structural, at HEI-level organised online questionnaires.
- At least once every three years, though preferably yearly, every EC organizes a conclave or a "teachersday". During this day there is room to reflect on the curriculum, content, profiling, evaluation policy, etc. The inclusion of the professors during this process of reflection enhances their sense of ownership and involvement, which is crucial when creating a culture of quality. The organisation and approach of these activities is in the hands of the ECs. During the preparation as well as during the activities, the FEDU can provide substantial support if desired.
- Every EC maintains relations with industry through Industrial Advisory Boards (IAR). At those consultations, the EC asks feedback on its programme(s) and its alumni. These

² See <http://www.jointquality.nl/> for the Dublin descriptors

conversations typically concern necessary programme content and required knowledge and skills. Furthermore, a work field event is regularly organised by the Faculty. The approach and working of the IAR is also in the hands of the EC, but the organisation of the work field event is entirely in the hands of the Faculty.

- (Recently graduated) Alumni are evaluated every year by the central services of the University. The evaluation contains questions regarding their education as well as employment. The Faculty set up an alumni evaluation with a wider reach during the last CTI-cycle (spring 2015). The alumni were split up into three groups: recently graduated, graduated less than five years ago, graduated more than five years ago. The evaluation contained generic questions at Faculty level and more specific questions at the level of the EC. The evaluation had been initiated by the FEDU in close consultation with the ECs. The response rate was relatively low. The Faculty is reflecting on a new method that would make it possible to keep in touch with the alumni more efficiently. Additionally, the Faculty is analysing if there are alternatives for this large-scale evaluation.
- Different groups of employees, which are involved with the programmes, are invited annually by the Faculty:
 - Almost every teaching assistant (TAs), mainly PhD students, take on curricular assignments ranging from organizing exercise sessions, coaching teamwork, guiding master's theses, etc.
 - Student counsellors and ombudspersons also are invited every semester for a meeting.
 - Administrative support staff of all the different programmes also meet twice a year with the vice-dean, the FEDU and the Faculty Administrators, to inform them about Faculty policy but also to make sure they feel involved in the Faculty quality assurance system.

Another cornerstone of the Faculty's quality assurance system is the investment in a balanced and well-considered curriculum development. Since the ECs are responsible for the curriculum of its programme(s), it is obvious that activities concerning curriculum development are conducted in the context of the EC. However, to lessen the workload of programme directors, the coordination, logistics and documentation is done by the FEDU.

As discussed earlier, the Faculty chose a three step approach based on the ACQA-framework. Firstly, the programme outcomes for each programme are formulated according to the seven areas of competence, described in AQCA, which results in similar structured programme outcomes for all programmes without losing each programme's unique character. Based on the formulated programme outcomes, curriculum mappings are conducted. Such curriculum mappings visualize the link between the programme outcomes, the content and evaluation of individual courses. This entailed that each teacher responsible for a course, was provided with the programme outcomes that were formulated during the first phase. Through a custom made online tool teachers indicated whether the outlined competences were practiced in the course and whether they were assessed as well. [10]

In a next step, the teachers have determined the distribution of the study load over the seven areas of competences. Based on this data ACQA-competence profiles are drawn up for all programmes or parts of programmes (e.g. only a certain option of a programme). These profiles allow the ECs and FEC to describe its different curricula in a uniform way. Finally the ECTS-course descriptions of all courses are composed accordingly. Important to acknowledge is the fact that this final step, together with the curriculum mappings, includes all teachers, not only the ones involved in the EC.

By checking a course's ECTS-course description and course-specific programme outcomes against the programme outcomes as described for the entire curriculum, a programme can check whether the intended curriculum matches the realised curriculum. Potential overlaps can be spotted and possibly superfluous courses can be eliminated from the curriculum.

Evaluation, learning method and programme outcomes can be matched a lot more accurately when working with completed curriculum mappings and streamlined programme outcomes. All these exercises are initiated every six years, but in case of major programme changes (some of) these exercises might be organized sooner.

The results of all these exercises are concluded in the programmes' blueprint, a document in which the university's as well as the Faculty's vision on education is translated to the programmes vision and profile. This document is updated every three years and revised every six years, in a cooperation between EC and FEC, supported and guided by the FEDU.

Besides the structural exercises concerning curriculum development, the results of other, more ad hoc exercises as feasibility analyses, ad hoc (student)hearings, etc... are also taken into account every step of the process.

In conclusion, the faculty believes that through this three-step approach higher levels of transparency, uniformity and efficiency are reached in the quality assurance process.

As already stated, the quality assurance system of the Faculty is based on two important pillars: large involvement of all the primary actors on the one hand and well thought-out developments of the curriculum on the other. All reports and results of the questionnaires and exercises conducted in this perspective are discussed at the EC. In this way, all these results serve as direct input for the programme specific SER and programme action plan. Generic aspects, general points of attention or questions regarding policy are transferred to the FEC, where they deliver input for the faculty action plan and SER on their part.

The programme specific SER is drawn up every six years, or every three years in case of an unfavourable visitation, while the programme action plan functions as a permanent instrument. The state of affairs of the action points that are put forward in the plan are discussed at least once a year by the EC that is responsible. In addition, the programme action plan as a whole is brought up to date and adjusted yearly on the basis of results of questionnaires and exercises. The Faculty action plan is updated and completed analogously at the yearly FEC conclave.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Both accreditation systems discussed, strive for the installation of a strong, broadly embedded quality culture. The programme accreditation performed by CTI comprises an important institutional component, since all the degrees of the Faculty were concerned in a single round. This approach fits well in the COBRA system, built around three levels, adding the university wide level to the faculty and programme level focused on in the CTI approach.

The HEI quality assurance system, COBRA, is based on regular reflection meetings with stakeholders, with a strong emphasis on student participation. CTI adds a transnational component to it, with visitation panels composed of international educational and domain experts. Next to stakeholder involvement, CTI focuses strongly on curriculum development. The latter is of importance since this Faculty of Engineering Science is embedded in an HEI built on the "von Humboldt"-model: research-driven with strong emphasis on scientific excellence and academic freedom of their academic staff in research and lectures [12]. In context of quality assurance this might become a thread for establishing a culture of quality assurance, which is built on dialogue and objectives at programme level and not at the level of the individual course. That is why the Faculty felt that a strong involvement of stakeholders was not sufficient to truly create a culture of quality assurance and acknowledged the importance of well-considered curriculum development as a means for quality development than mere administration and regulation.

The efforts made during the first CTI-cycle clearly initiated an increasing culture of quality assurance and created a stronger involvement of the stakeholders at programme level. This awareness was further sparked by the implementation of the HEI-system COBRA. The Faculty has high hopes that these developments will not be temporary but aspires to establish

them further and more structural by implementing the above described integrated quality assurance system were benefits of both accreditation systems are combined.

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